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METHODOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING: USING THE EXAMPLE OF TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS

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KASBBIY PEDAGOGIK TA'LIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASI: KELAJAK O'QITUVCHILARNI TAYYORLASH NAMALIDAN FOYDALANISH.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мазкур мақолада муаллиф педагогика соҳасида малакали кадрлар тайёрлаш жараёнида хозирги кунда долзарб бўлган муаммолар ҳамда камчилик ва номуносибликларни таҳлил қилган. Хорижий ва маҳаллий тадқиқотчилар ишларини ўрганган ҳолда педагогнинг касбий тайёргарлиги ва унга қўйилаётган талаблар, замонавий таълимни ташкил этиш тамойилларини очиқ беришга ҳаракат қилган.

МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ: НА ПРИМЕРЕ ПОДГОТОВКИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье автор проанализировал актуальные проблемы, недостатки и несоответствия в процессе подготовки квалифицированных кадров в педагогической сфере. Изучив работы зарубежных и отечественных исследователей, он попытался раскрыть профессиональную подготовку педагога и требования к нему а так же принципы организации современного образовательного процесса.

ANNOTATION

In this article, the author analyzed the current problems, shortcomings and inconsistencies in the process of training qualified personnel in the pedagogical field. Having studied the work of foreign and domestic researchers, he tried to reveal the professional training of the teacher and the requirements for him, as well as the principles of organizing the modern educational process.

Калит сўзлар Касбий тайёргарлик, компетенция, таълим тизимини ташкил этиш, ҳамкорлик, инновация

Ключевые слова Профессиональная подготовка, компетентность, организация образовательной системы, сотрудничество, инновации

Keywords Professional training, competence, organization of the educational system, cooperation, innovation

At the present stage of the development of society, one of the global tasks of pedagogical science is to determine the methods, forms and ways to improve the efficiency of training specialists, and its solution is the most important condition for accelerating the entire educational complex, rational formation, development and use of the skills of university graduates. Quantitative and qualitative changes in the development of society and the economy change the basic requirements for the education system. In this regard, there is a need to review the current state of formation and continuous development of students' professional training and to identify new innovative, effective ways. Unfortunately, the existing and widely used approach to the definition and analysis of students' professional training, based on the volume of students' knowledge, does not meet the quality requirements of a new stage in the training of modern competitive specialists and the acceleration of the educational process.

Insufficient analysis of the problem under study and the lack of effective ways to solve this problem do not allow all stakeholders to take a comprehensive and systematic approach to managing the training process and negatively affect the effectiveness of education. This is mainly due to the lack of necessary information about modern requirements for personnel training, the formation and development of students' professional training, and effective methods for determining competence.

In the process of practical activity, a practitioner plays a special role. As K.D.Ushinsky noted: "If pedagogy wants to educate a comprehensively developed person, then first of all it must fully know him." [1,15]

In general, the fact that the requirements and the effectiveness of their preparation are not systematically determined is not related to the general indicators of the higher education system, the actualization of the research process on this problem under study has caused a discrepancy between the existing conditions in the professional and

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pedagogical training of students and the need for jobs. This is also one of the reasons arising from modern market requirements in the system of training and retraining of personnel.

The problem of training personnel necessary for the country's economy can only be solved in close cooperation between the educational institution and enterprises, which requires the creation of a system that can influence the content of the employer's educational program and order exclusive specialists focused on a particular enterprise, as well as the availability of a training base at the university. The educational institution will have the opportunity to "check" the quality and level of preparation of their students. [2]

The indicator of the quality of training of specialists can be presented in two stages, one of its sides summarizes the parameters and characteristics of the educational process, during which the student is given certain professional qualities and a set of characteristics - the quality of training of specialists by the university ("potential quality"), and the other - activity of the enterprise and the level of its development in dependence ("necessary quality") is determined by the enterprise as an integral indicator of its requirements for a quality employee. [3]

The formation of professional pedagogical readiness and competitiveness of students in the labor market is necessary to ensure their high level of training. This task cannot be performed only on the territory of educational institutions. The reason is that for a comprehensive and systematic formulation of the problem, advanced technologies are needed, special educational and scientific laboratories for research, material and technical base for organizing practical classes. In order to create an educational environment that allows students to use such advanced resources, it is advisable for higher education institutions to take relationships with partner organizations, such as research institutes and industrial organizations, to a new, innovative level.

The analysis showed that important theoretical provisions on the main directions of modernization of teacher education, presented in the framework of different methodological approaches, do not always correspond to each other. This makes it difficult to develop a holistic concept that reveals all issues related to the creation of an innovative educational environment in educational institutions and the development of professional and pedagogical training of students in it.

As Aristotle said: "The mind consists not only in knowledge, but also in the ability to apply knowledge in practice." Despite the fact that this idea appeared a long time ago, it has recently been actively used in modern pedagogy. ... Until recently, the level of graduate training was considered as the presence of certain knowledge, skills, and in the new conditions, this view is understood as the formation of certain general professional and professional competencies among students. Thus, a student's professional and pedagogical education is considered as a holistic system process only when the ability to form a holistic algorithm for performing a non-standard task using elements of knowledge and skills acquired to date to solve typical tasks of pedagogical activity is realized. From this we can conclude that readiness is the ability to form elements of knowledge and skills acquired at the moment for solving typical tasks, in the form of a holistic algorithm for performing a non-standard task. [4]

This means that "readiness is the ability of a specialist to find optimal solutions to various situations that may arise in his professional activity, and professionally perform any functional tasks." [5]

As a result of scientific and pedagogical analysis and our research work, the following pedagogical conditions for the development of professional pedagogical training were determined: a) designing the development process of professional pedagogical training based on innovative cooperation; b) determination and improvement of the effectiveness of the results of professional pedagogical activity of future teachers; c) assessment of the current level of development of professional pedagogical readiness; g) improving the content of education on the basis of mutual integration of functional, system-structural approaches and advanced foreign experience; г) повышать качество программ и ресурсов, служащих развитию профессиональной компетентности на основе мотивационно-коррекционных подходов.

This process should be carried out on the basis of the following principles:

1. Orientation of the content and forms of education to the individual;
2. Professional orientation of the content of the subject;
3. Complex thematic organization of educational material;
4. Conscious comparative analysis of topics;
5. Systematic variability of forms, methods and styles of teaching;
6. Modeling - professional adaptation of game methods.

This model of organization of education allows, on the one hand, to take into account the emerging needs of the labor market in the development of a system of continuous education, and on the other hand, to implement joint educational programs and develop professional pedagogical training.

Innovative cooperation in a pedagogical university changes the place and role of the educational process in the system of professional pedagogical training of a future teacher, shows ways to strengthen its component, and makes it possible to determine a new look at the development of important moments in the formation of students' professional pedagogical readiness in the educational process. This approach has a significant heuristic potential and is a source of new pedagogical ideas, technologies, creates the necessary conditions for building a methodological base.

The effectiveness of the proposed model depends on the goals and practical tasks of improving the professional pedagogical readiness of future teachers, as well as on the organizational and pedagogical conditions that predict the availability of material, technical, financial, information and human resources in a pedagogical university.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Ушинский К.Д. Педагогические произведения, М.: Педагогика, 1990 150 с.
2. Андреев, В.И. Педагогика высшей школы. Инновационно - прогностический курс: учеб. пособие/ В.И. Андреев.-Казань: Центр инновационных технологий.- 2008.-500 с.
3. Зеер, Э. Ф. Психология профессионального развития: учеб. пособие / Э. Ф. Зеер .- 2-е изд., стер. - М. : Академия, 2007. - 240 с.
4. Kh.A.Umarov Analysis of approaches to the formation of professional readiness of students in uzbekistan (on the example of future teachers) PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION (2021) 58(1): pages 3535-3541
5. Kh.A.Umarov Incessancy of education and activities in the development of professional education “The american journal of social science and education innovations” pages 256-263 <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajssei/Volume02Issue07-33>

